

Simulated Environments and Environmental Consciousness:

Extending Ecoacoustic Monitoring into Sound Art

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Abstract

This article explores how greater interplay between science, technology, and art can facilitate deeper connectedness with nature and large, distributed natural processes, such as global warming and avian migration. The author, an ecoacoustic data scientist and musician, lays a foundation by discussing how the sublime aesthetic characterizes our appreciation of nature, the myriad benefits of nature immersion, and the ability of art—particularly sound art—to facilitate a connection with natural hyperobjects. The author then applies these concepts in several sound art pieces derived from bird detections within the *Sound of Norway*, a national-scale passive acoustic monitoring network.

Technology, Ecology, and Connectedness to Nature

Recent technological advances in computing and sensing have enabled revolutionary new approaches for monitoring ecosystems. Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM), an ecological method growing in popularity and showcased in this paper, leverages autonomous (often solar-powered) acoustic recorders and machine-learning algorithms to automate the detection of species vocalizations in-situ [1], enabling ecologists to compile high resolution data to study migration dynamics [2] and human impacts on biodiversity or animal behavior [3]. Such technology effectively expands ecologists' senses over vast distances and long time periods, supplementing in-person surveys.

Outside of ecological research, technological advancement is clearly not a panacea for socio-environmental harmony, as the increasing prevalence of digital technology and digital media environments has led to a loss in nature connectedness [4], the “stable state of consciousness comprising symbiotic cognitive, affective, and experiential traits that reflect, through consistent attitudes and behaviors, a sustained awareness of the interrelatedness between one’s self and the rest of nature” [5-6]. With myriad studies underscoring the positive effects of nature connectedness on attention [7-9], stress [10], and even life satisfaction [11], these trends are concerning, to say the least. Technology seemingly provides us with a greater scientific understanding of nature while simultaneously dissociating us from it.

Reversing such widespread disassociation from nature should particularly concern conservationists. In their work *Connectedness as a Core Conservation Concern*, Zylstra et al present the argument that nature connectedness builds upon both scientific understanding of nature as well as actual experience and immersion within nature, eventually leading to environmentally responsible behavior [12-13]. Malcolm Budd makes a parallel point in *The Aesthetic Appreciation of Nature*: “aesthetic appreciation is deeper the more it is penetrated by and the product of [scientific] knowledge” [14], suggesting that scientific understand of nature’s processes helps one appreciate nature as nature and not as an art object [15]. Through a scientific understanding of bird migration, for example, a person living in the northern hemisphere may form a greater appreciation and respect for birds that arrive in the spring, knowing the vast distances they have traveled. Thus, the bio-environmental sciences form a foundation for us to understand our relation to nature and appreciate its processes and vast spatiotemporal scales. However, as any climate scientist may tell you, scientific understanding alone cannot facilitate collective action on environmental issues.

The massive spatiotemporal scale of natural processes presents an impediment to increasing collective nature connectedness and pro-environmental action. Timothy Morton frames environmental concepts such as ecosystems or global warming as “hyperobjects,” defined as objects “massively distributed in time and space relative to humans” [16], thereby making them only partially accessible to our senses and difficult to relate to emotionally or aesthetically. Indeed, the fact that we can only perceive a “small time slice” [17] of an ecosystem presents a problem for the appreciation of the aesthetic value of that ecosystem. Art plays a critical role in overcoming (or at least alleviating) this issue by immersing us within natural hyperobjects in creative ways. An oft-cited example of ecological art, the 2015 piece *Ice Watch* by Olafur Eliasson and Minik Rosing,

consists of twelve large pieces of ice carved from the Greenland ice sheet, installed near the COP21 climate summit in Paris [18]. Passersby could interact freely with the piece as it gradually melted onto the pavement, a tactile and direct experience with the hyperobject of global warming [19]. One may compare this aesthetic experience to an analogous scientific one, such as using remotely sensed imagery from satellites to derive rates of ice sheet retreat over time in Greenland. Scientists may use technology to study nature at huge scales, but deriving nature connectedness solely from data and associated graphs seems challenging at best. It again becomes clear how science provides a critical knowledge-base upon which art can facilitate the development of our “relationship to non-humans” [20].

In this paper, I first establish the importance of the sublime aesthetic for establishing connectedness with and appreciation of natural hyperobjects, and then discuss how art may leverage technology to act as an extension of nature, expanding our senses and ability to experience these hyperobjects, providing examples of notable previous work. I then endeavor to enact these principles by leveraging soundscapes and bird detections derived from the national-scale PAM project, the *Sound of Norway* [21-22]. By using these distributed acoustic sensors in tandem with a generative audio scheme, I mimic long-term temporal flows of soundscapes across the latitudinal extent of Norway in a compressed form, allowing listeners to experience the hyperobjects of large-scale forest soundscapes and avian migration in a previously impossible way. Through this effort, I contend that art can contribute to bridging the gap between scientific understanding and nature connectedness.

Perception of Nature and Art

In the 18th century, Kant classified aesthetic experiences (or perceptual experiences appreciated for their own sake) into the *beautiful* and the *sublime*, useful frameworks for teasing apart aesthetic experiences of art and nature [23]. The *beautiful*, generally confined to a bounded object such as a painting or sculpture, may elicit pleasure through a judgment of taste or quality. Conversely, the *sublime* references the quantity and unboundedness of an aesthetic experience invoked by nature. It raises an indirect or “negative pleasure” [24], characterized both by the inability of our senses to perceive nature in its entirety and the potential of the human mind to comprehend nature’s scales in a scientific sense. The sublime aesthetic thus conveys “admiration

and respect” [25] for nature while revealing the potential of our minds to expand past our immediate senses. For Kant, the sublime experience of nature can be invoked by both its vast spatiotemporal scales (the mathematical sublime) [26] and its incredible power (the dynamic sublime) [27]. Here, we build our discussion upon the concept of the mathematical sublime.

In the 20th century, scientists, philosophers, and the public became increasingly aware of deleterious effects of industrialization and overconsumption on the natural world. The field of environmental aesthetics re-emerged alongside the conservation movement as a reaction to this [28]. In a seminal work by Ronald Hepburn in 1966, *Contemporary Aesthetics and the Neglect of Natural Beauty* [29], the author argues that contemporary aesthetics had focused too greatly on the art world, and suggests that modern approaches to nature appreciation incorporate “approaches that accommodate not only nature’s indeterminate and varying character, but also both our multi-sensory experience and our diverse understanding of it” [30]. We typically find art-objects markedly separated from their surroundings via a frame, a stage, or a velvet rope. These boundaries lend a sense of distinctness and completeness, starkly in contrast with the ambiguity and vastness of the natural world. In a nature-experience, we are “*in* nature and a part *of* nature, we do not stand over against it as over against a painting on a wall” [31], this immersive aspect of nature arguably provides a space for self-experience and self-reflection, even facilitating feelings of “one-ness”.

The seeking in nature for art-object qualities, such as the *picturesque* (imagine a postcard of Yosemite or Mount Everest) and the finite, arguably lead to an unappreciation of the whole and thus an inability to experience the sublime or derive a sense of one-ness from nature experience. Blurring typical art-object boundaries thus allows for a more authentic extension of the natural sublime to occur. This can be accomplished through playing with immersion, scale, and perspective in a variety of mediums. Sound art becomes especially relevant here, as the medium of sound lends itself to “works that are space-shaping and space-claiming in nature” [32-33].

Extending Nature with Simulated Environments

One may argue that the most sublime perceptions of real nature are those which hint at its vastness. The view from a coastal cliff, for example, reveals the curvature of the earth, hinting at laws of gravity which form planets and galaxies. While one can undoubtedly experience the sublimity of the natural world through one’s own vision, hearing, smell, and touch, some aspects of the natural

world are more difficult to aesthetically integrate than others. Ecosystems, for example, are somewhat fuzzy environmental hyperobjects that extend over large spatial distances, cycle over variable time periods (diurnal, annual, etc.), and consist of many interweaving biological relationships. Our sensory limitations prevent us from fully aesthetically appreciating the totality of ecosystems' spatial and temporal scales, as we might for an artwork such as a painting, a book, or a film [34]. Perhaps this inability to experience the totality of an ecosystem aesthetically impedes a full appreciation of natural beauty and, thereby, the development of environmental consciousness. This applies equally to other environmental hyperobjects such as forests, species migration, or global warming. Indeed, research indicates that aesthetic appreciation of nature strengthens nature connectedness [35], which has been identified as a key driver of pro-environmental behaviors [36].

Expanding the potential scope of our aesthetic experience may strengthen our connectedness with hyperobjects like ecosystems or our emotional integration of wicked problems like global warming. Art enables us to aesthetically experience such hyperobjects from new angles and in compressed forms, potentially developing an emotional connection to these broad and diffuse concepts. Art mediums which can leverage digital technology, such as virtual reality and sound art, have a critical role to play, due to their innate ability to stretch and compress space and time. However, these technologies would be erroneously viewed as replacements for nature; they instead offer an “extension of nature” [37] that supplements our existing natural experiences with novel viewpoints or shifts of scale. Still, studies have shown that these extensions of nature can bestow some of the beneficial psychological effects of actual nature immersion. Listening to natural soundscapes has been shown to facilitate stress recovery [38-39], and a review of virtual reality nature by Sharon Frost et al identified several studies associating it with decrease in negative feelings such as fear or anxiety [40], though more research is needed in this area.

Notable Previous Works

The virtual reality art piece, *The Bone* [41], led conceptually by Chilean artist Michelle-Marie Letelier, utilizes visual cues, soundscapes, and spoken word to create an empathetic experience between the viewer and an animal subject. Sitting physically inside an old wooden fishing boat, the viewer puts on a VR headset and enters the 3D-rendered skull of a real wild salmon, while a traditional Sámi Joik song echoes in the background. A human voice echoes inside the skull, a stream of consciousness interpretation of the memories of this deceased wild salmon's life and

freedom, soon contrasted with the memories of its brethren who spent their lives in a factory fish farm environment. Immersion in this “intermediate world—between deep sea and universe; between present, future or past; between reality, dream or utopia” [42] pushes the viewer to experience for themselves this contrast and to consider how humans impact the lived experiences of animals from a novel perspective.

The sound art piece *Explorations of Extraction and Decay* [43] by Merlin Coleman was performed at the spatial audio theatre Audium in San Francisco from 2023-2024 and exemplifies how spatialized sound art can effectively facilitate a connection between our emotions and broad socioenvironmental realities. The piece takes place in two settings, a quarry and a landfill, embodying concepts of resource extraction and waste disposal, respectively. In each of these settings, Coleman interweaves field recordings of industrial excavators and dumping with snippets of conversations with concerned locals affected and concerned by these operations including local government employees and ecologists, using the spatial aspect of the theatre’s speakers to create tension and release through the hectic or slow movement of sound sources and the illusions of them approaching or departing from the listener. Brief but impactful musical interjections appear all around the listener, capturing and expounding upon the emotions that underlie their concerns of environmental destruction and pollution, emotions that are difficult to capture solely in words. In these ways, Coleman ties these processes of environmental extraction and waste dumping to human emotion, allowing the listener to aesthetically relate to these large-scale processes that we may hear of more commonly in drier scientific or journalistic fashions.

The piece *Longplayer* by Jem Finer [44] demonstrates how sound art excels at “attuning our senses to superhuman timescales” [45]. Beginning on December 31, 1999, six audio tracks started to play an identical musical piece in parallel at varying rates in a cycle not again aligning until the piece’s end in 2999 [46]. During a 2020 live performance of *Longplayer* in Amsterdam, Netherlands, one could experience the expansive timescales and slow evolution of the piece beside the typical hectic sounds of traffic in the city center outside [47]. *Longplayer* serves to remind the listener that hyperobjects unfold on long timescales alongside our daily lives and short-term concerns.

As with temporal scales, sound art facilitates our access to otherwise inaccessible spatial scales and perspectives. *Listening at the Seams* by Steven Hammer and Greg Sieber [48] uses sound objects to elucidate the effect of human development and pollution on the Schuylkill River in Pennsylvania.

In one arrangement, the artists mix audio from microphones placed in discarded shotgun shells and a half-melted plastic bottle with recordings from a hydrophone in the river's headwaters. The natural textures of water flow and bird song contrast with the artificial resonances of the plastic bottle and tubing, encompassing the environmental history of the river in a way inaccessible via a standard listening experience. Works such as *Listening at the Seams* and Bernie Krause's *The Great Animal Orchestra* [49]—which involve the collection and arrangement of nature field recordings—begin to blur the lines between sound art and scientific documentation of the natural environment. The artists curate (as opposed to create) their pieces from the sounds of nature, assembling these sounds into forms which allow listeners to perceive nature beyond what bodily senses allow.

Case Study: The Sound of Norway

The *Sound of Norway* initiative, undertaken by ornithologists and data scientists at the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research, explores the capability of PAM to track biodiversity, rare species, and migratory dynamics over a national scale. During my PhD, I participated in the planning and field work for this initiative, deploying several dozen autonomous recorders in Norwegian forests during the spring of 2022 (see Fig. 1a), through which over 37,000 hours of recordings were collected. These solar-powered stations (see Fig. 1b) used the Bugg platform [50] to collect audio at 44.1 KHz, which was saved with a compressed MP3 encoding in five-minute increments. The stations with reliable 4G cellular network access transmitted this audio to a cloud server, where we applied the BirdNET algorithm [51] to detect bird calls and identify species, splicing shorter audio files for each identification in the process. Our scientific goals included mapping changes in the species vocalization probability during their migratory arrival in the spring and understanding how automation could fill gaps in manual bird surveys (see our preprint for more information [52]). However, the capturing of a vast number of ecological recordings over a large spatiotemporal scale lent itself naturally to studying these natural hyperobjects from an artistic angle as well.

Figure 1 – a) Map of *Sound of Norway* recording stations and total hours recorded per region. Norway shapefile sourced from Robert Hijmans [53]. b) Photo by author of a passive acoustic monitoring station with solar panel and Bugg recording device, set up as part of the *Sound of Norway* project.

A mixture of programmatic and random, generative techniques was applied in the curation of the three sound art pieces showcased here from environmental recordings. Using Python, I downloaded up to 30 random detected bird calls with a BirdNET confidence score over 0.50 (based on a scale from 0.0-1.0) for each combination of recording station, four-hour period of the day, and month (May, June, and July). To lessen background noise from the recordings, I captured a noise print from a silent example in Adobe Audition and applied its Noise Reduction Process tool with standard settings. In Ableton Live 11, a Sampler instrument was created for each period-region-month combination, and the corresponding samples were loaded into these Sampler instruments.

For the southernmost recording stations, those in forests near Kristiansand and Stavanger, the Sampler instruments were panned to the left of the recording. The northernmost ones, outside Tromsø and Finnmark, were panned far to the right (see Fig. 2). The center of the mix contains bird calls from Bergen, Lillehammer, and Trondheim. For each four-hour period, bird calls were randomly triggered for the Sampler instruments in each region for approximately 20 seconds, with

time in between triggered calls also randomized. After 20 seconds, bird calls captured during the next four-hour period were faded in, and the process continued as such. This procedure resulted in three sound art pieces accompanying this paper as supplementary material—*Norway Forests: May, June, July*—each of which portray a compressed version of the Norwegian forest biosphere hyperobject in the months of the avian migratory arrival and breeding season in Norway. The pieces are freely available in the Supplemental Information and on Zenodo [54].

Figure 2 – Combined regional soundscapes for *Norway Forests: May* piece. The y-axis represents left-right panning of the regions in the stereo field, corresponding to the

relative latitudes of each region. The x-axis represents the relation between time of day where bird detections were sampled and the length of the piece.

Migrating birds begin arriving across Norway in the early spring. First, short-distance migrants such as Starlings (*Sturnus vulgaris*) and Thrushes, followed by long-distance migrants such as Willow Warbler (*Phylloscopus trochilus*) and Spotted Flycatcher (*Muscicapa striata*) in April and May, when migration activity peaks [55]. Likewise, vocalization frequency peaks upon migratory arrival in May, as individuals compete for territory and mates, and then tends to decrease through June and July [56]. However, Norway stretches widely across latitudes, with northern and more mountainous regions generally receiving migrants later in the season when snow has melted. The *Norway Forests, May* piece showcases these broader trends. At our highest elevation recorders in the Lillehammer region, we only detected species during the dawn chorus, generally the period of highest diurnal vocal activity (see Fig. 2). Additionally, southern regions such as Kristiansand and Bergen showed generally denser biophony—the collective acoustic signals generated by species—than northern regions such as Finnmark and Tromsø, which have sparser but sustained vocal activity, potentially due to the longer days in the north. In these northern areas, the sun never sets during June, with southern areas like Oslo and Kristiansand only receiving a few hours of twilight. This large-scale phenomenon becomes apparent through the panned audio in *Norway Forests* pieces, particularly in *June* and *July* where the “weight” of the pieces shifts slightly to the right ear towards the end of the piece in the evenings, representing the sustained vocal activity in the northern regions where the sun is not setting.

Future Work

Further explorations on this theme could involve extending this piece, currently optimized for headphones or stereo speakers, into a physical setting for public listening. One may imagine a room or hallway lined with speakers, along which listeners could walk and experience the full soundscapes of Norway in a compressed spatiotemporal fashion. Such an idea was explored effectively by David Dunn et al in 2020 when presenting playback of parallel multi-channel recordings done of a lake ecosystem in Northern California [57]. Speakers were placed in a room at similar relative distances and locations to the original recorders at the lake, allowing the public

to experience both their own extended acoustic sense of this ecosystem as well as multiple points of audition (analogous to the visual concept of point of view), enabling them “to move through the space to perceive local nested details while still hearing the total soundscape that surrounds them.” [58]. This style of playback allows listeners to easily traverse spatial scales of acoustically recorded environmental hyperobjects.

While the decision to use audio splices of bird detections was used in *Norway Forests* due to the relative lack of biophony density and recording quality in our Norwegian recordings, future pieces may consider using raw soundscape data like Dunn et al to more accurately portray spatial biophony patterns. A similar scheme to the spatial art pieces demonstrated here could also be applied to an aesthetic study of development gradients. For example, a series of microphones could record at increasing distances from development into an undeveloped forest and spatially panned for a listener, showcasing how anthropogenic forces reduce acoustic complexity and the biodiversity of vocalizing species [59].

Conclusion

Inspired by earlier sound art works, my motivation behind *Norway Forests: May, June, July* was to enable an otherwise impossible aesthetic experience of large-scale natural hyperobjects: annual bird migration, climate, and forest ecosystems, that has perhaps previously not been done at this scale. These works (and simulated environments in general) act as an extension of natural aesthetics [60] that facilitate our appreciation of nature’s sublimity. Ecologists—especially those collecting audio, images, or video of nature through their research—may consider collaborations with artists as a means of developing an emotional depth to scientific communication. The aesthetic, emotional dimension of nature connectedness that art can facilitate weaves well together with our scientific understanding of nature, together offering a more complete nature connectedness. In this way, art may reconnect science, which is often of a cerebral nature, back to the emotional level on which we often operate, both individually and collectively. However, while offering potential benefits, simulated nature cannot be regarded as a replacement for proper nature (see [61]) and artists and programmers creating such nature “extensions” should remain humble. As stated by EO Wilson in *Biophilia*: “Artifacts are incomparably poorer than the life they are designed to mimic. They are only a mirror to our thoughts” [62].

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References and Notes

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